

Bayesian optimal sensor placement for acoustic emission source localization with clusters of sensors in isotropic plates

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Abstract

For practical applications of acoustic emission (AE) source localization, it is extremely important to optimally place the sensors, i.e., the sensors should be placed such that they gather the most effective information - leading to highly accurate localization of AE sources. In this paper, a Bayesian optimal sensor placement strategy is used to determine the optimal (and worst) positions of sensor clusters for AE source localization in isotropic plates with unknown material properties. The sensor clusters are composed of three sensors arranged in a right-angle triangular configuration, and the AE source localization strategy employed requires placement of at least 2 sensor clusters. In the work presented here, three different hot-spot (source location) areas are analyzed, and the best and worst clusters positions are predicted for the placement of 2, 3 and 4 sensors clusters. The optimization required to arrive at the optimal positions is performed using exhaustive search method, heuristic search methods and genetic algorithms. Furthermore, theoretical validation - using Bayesian inference with simulated data - and experimental validation - using AE source localization methodology and Bayesian inference with experimental data - are presented to validate the predictions by the Bayesian optimal sensor placement.

Keywords: AE source localization, Bayesian optimal sensor placement, Bayesian inference, information gain, Kullback-Leibler divergence

1. Introduction

Acoustic Emission (AE) is a term that describes a class of naturally occurring phenomena wherein transient acoustic (elastic) waves are generated from localized or distributed source(s) [1]. AE sources are a consequence of deformation and fracture processes like cracks, dislocations, inclusions, corrosion, delamination, etc., and are associated with the release of energy. A part of this energy is transformed into transient acoustic (elastic) waves that propagate from the source(s) to the surfaces of the medium as AEs. Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) techniques based on AE find attractive applicability in scrutinizing the integrity of various engineering structures [2]. These monitoring techniques employ a network of spatially-distributed sensors to capture/record AEs as AE signals. The captured AE signals are subsequently used to localize the AE sources. As AE sources are potential locations of damage, it becomes pertinent to localize them at an early stage with sufficient accuracy, thus making AE source localization an integral aspect of AE monitoring techniques.

AE source localization can be achieved through various different strategies. Over the recent years, lot of different AE source localization methodologies have been reported. Tobias [3] proposed a triangulation technique based on the difference in time of arrival of the AE signals at the spatially distributed AE sensors. This method, however, works only with isotropic plates whose material properties are known, i.e., a prior knowledge of the wave speed is needed. To localize the AE source in anisotropic plates, Kundu et al. [4, 5, 6] proposed an approach based on solving a system of non-linear equations using an optimization algorithm. This method requires *a priori* knowledge of the direction dependent velocity profile in the plate. The knowledge of the plate properties (and thus the velocity profile) is not always available *a priori*. To

overcome this, Kundu et al. [7] proposed an AE source localization method - with L-shaped sensor cluster arrangement - for anisotropic plates that neither requires solving a system of non-linear equations nor a prior knowledge of the direction dependent velocity profile in the plate. The method proposed in [7] has been shown to be working for AE source localization in isotropic plates with unknown properties. The AE source localization method proposed by Ciampa et al. [8, 9] localizes AE source in anisotropic plates without the prior knowledge of the plate properties. However, this method, unlike the approach reported in [7], requires the solution of a system of non-linear equations. Xiao et al. [10] proposed a beamforming method to localize AE sources in anisotropic plates without knowing the properties of the plate. In all the aforementioned methods, the assumption of straight line wave propagation from the AE source to the sensors was used. Such an assumption results in significantly inaccurate source localizations for complex and highly anisotropic structures [11]. Several AE source localization methods that do not assume straight line wave propagation have been reported for structures with unknown properties. Baxter et al. [12] reported on an AE source localization methodology for complex structures wherein, owing to the complex structure, the wave propagation paths are not linear. Hensman et al. [13] improved the method reported in [12] by proposing the use of Gaussian process (GP) regression. Recently, Jones et al. [14] extended the use of Gaussian process regression and reported on a Bayesian methodology for AE source localization in complex structures. To localize AE sources in highly anisotropic plates with unknown material properties, Park et al. [11] used the L-shaped sensor cluster arrangement reported in [7] with a wave front shaped-based approach. Two wave front shapes in highly anisotropic plates, namely, rhombus and ellipse, were analyzed. In [15], Sen and Kundu provided a more general parametric curve-based approach, and also modified the elliptical wave front-based approach reported in [11]. To provide an improved alternative to L-shaped sensor clusters for highly anisotropic plates, Sen et al. [16] reported on the use of square-shaped sensor clusters with the wave-front shaped based approach. More recently, Sen and Kundu [17] proposed a signal energy-based approach for AE source localization in orthotropic plates.

All AE source localization methods rely on AE signals recorded by the AE sensors placed on the structure. The accuracy of the AE source localization methods, thus, depends significantly on the information (i.e. AE signals) gathered by the sensors. The quality of the information recorded by the sensors varies depending on their locations. For practical applications, it is not possible to place the sensors throughout the whole structure. Therefore, it becomes extremely pertinent to optimally place the sensors, i.e., the sensors should be placed such that they gather the most effective information - leading to highly accurate localization of AE sources. Many different strategies predicting the optimal sensor placement for SHM purposes have been reported in literature. Among others, information theoretic measures provide useful criteria for objective function tailored for the target of the experiment. Udawadia [18] reported on a Fisher Information matrix (FIM) based optimal sensor placement method for parameter identification. Ye and Ni [19] proposed an optimal sensor placement technique based on information entropy for structural damage detection. In [20], Capellari et al. reported on an optimal sensor placement approach based on the expected Kullback–Liebler divergence (KL-div) and utility theory. An information entropy based approach for optimal sensor placement for reliable parameter estimation was introduced by Papadimitriou et al. [21] by extending the Bayesian model updating framework [22]. For large number of data, asymptotic approximations of the information entropy were introduced [21, 23]. When an exact solution of posterior can not be obtained easily, it was shown that asymptotic techniques are computationally efficient compared to sampling techniques [24] and are convenient with sufficient accuracy [25, 26]. Solutions to the problem of information redundancy obtained with closely spaced sensors were presented by introducing a correlation to the prediction error covariance matrix [25]. In [27], Yuen and Kuok proposed an efficient Bayesian sequential sensor placement algorithm based on robust information entropy for structural identification. Leyder et al. [28] reported on optimal sensor configurations for the modal identification of a post-tensioned timber frame structure while keeping the number of necessary sensors to a minimum. More recently, a methodology for optimal sensor configuration based on the value of information was reported in [29, 30], while Ercan et al. [31, 32] presented information entropy based optimal sensor placement strategies for virtual sensing. A thorough review of the different optimal sensor placement strategies for

SHM applications can be found in [33, 34].

Although optimal sensor placement techniques have been popularly studied for different aspects of SHM, their employment with AE source localization methods has not been reported. In this paper, a Bayesian optimal sensor placement strategy is employed to determine the optimal placement of sensor clusters that result in the best (i.e. most accurate) source localizations in isotropic plates with unknown properties. The sensor clusters are composed of three sensors arranged in a right-angle triangular configuration. Source location parameters and their uncertainties are estimated using a Bayesian optimal sensor placement strategy for parameter estimation, while the AE source localization strategy follows the method proposed in [7]. Although AE source locations are typically unknown, there exist critical areas where damage may appear (referred to as hot-spots). To localize the AE sources within the hot-spot areas, the AE localization strategy employed here requires the placement of at least 2 clusters. The study reported in this paper predicts the optimal positions of sensor clusters for three different hot-spot areas. These optimal positions are determined for the placement of 2, 3 and 4 clusters. The optimization - required to arrive at the optimal positions - is performed using exhaustive search method, heuristic search methods and genetic algorithms (GA). The latter two provide computationally effective near optimal solutions. The work presented here can be used to determine the optimal cluster positions for the placement of any number (> 2) of clusters, with any number and size of hot-spot area(s).

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows; Section 2 provides the overview of the AE source localization strategy used in this paper. Section 3 introduces the Bayesian optimal sensor placement strategy employed to determine the optimal cluster locations. In Section 4, the model setup is introduced followed by theoretical predictions of the optimal cluster placement for AE source localization. Furthermore, theoretical and experimental validation of the predictions is provided. The former involves using Bayesian inference with simulated data while the latter employs experimental data with AE source localization methodology and Bayesian inference. Finally, conclusions are drawn in Section 5.

2. AE source localization with n clusters of sensors

The formation, growth and propagation of cracks in solid structures are associated with release of energy in the form of elastic waves. These elastic waves propagate as acoustic emission signals from the crack area to the sensors as shown in Fig. 1. The sensors can be located at multiple locations and arranged in different configurations [35, 36, 16]. In this paper, a strategy with three-sensor clusters - able to identify the direction of arrival of the wave, without knowing material properties of the medium - is employed [11].

A right-angle triangular configuration of three sensors is used, as seen in Fig. 2, to predict the location of an acoustic emission source in a plate. This configuration is called a sensor *cluster* wherein the three sensors are placed orthogonally at points O , P_1 and P_2 with a distance B from the middle sensor located at O as shown in Fig. 2. The distance B should be small enough such that the dispersion-induced signal distortion over that propagation distance can be neglected. Also, d should be much smaller than the distance between the acoustic emission source and the respective sensor cluster so that the assumption of same angle of propagation from the source to the three sensors of the cluster can be made. A large distance between the source and the respective cluster also ensures the wave front passing through the cluster can be assumed a plane wave as shown in Fig. 2. Based on the signal analysis shown below, the output estimate of the α^{th} cluster is the direction of arrival angle θ_α . For an isotropic system, at least two ($n = 2$) angle estimates are required for source localization. With two angles computed from two different clusters known, one may find the predicted AE source location at the intersection of two lines drawn at the clusters positions.

For estimating the angle of arrival, it is assumed that a plane wave arrives at the α^{th} cluster location from the direction indicated in Fig. 2 by the red arrow. The angle θ_α , i.e. the direction of arrival, is computed based on the following procedure. First, the source direction vector, \vec{w}_α^\perp , and the parallel vector,

\vec{w}_α , of the plane wave front towards the point O are given as [11]

$$\begin{bmatrix} \vec{w}_\alpha^\perp, \vec{w}_\alpha \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -\cos \theta_\alpha & -\sin \theta_\alpha \\ -\sin \theta_\alpha & \cos \theta_\alpha \end{bmatrix}, \quad (1)$$

where θ_α is positive in the counter-clockwise direction. The direction of arrival can be determined from the four-quadrant inverse tangent with two time-difference-of-arrivals (TDOAs) as

$$\tan \theta_\alpha = \frac{\sin \theta_\alpha}{\cos \theta_\alpha} = \frac{v\Delta t_{\alpha 2}/B}{v\Delta t_{\alpha 1}/B} = \frac{\Delta t_{\alpha 2}}{\Delta t_{\alpha 1}} = \frac{t_{\alpha 2} - t_{\alpha 0}}{t_{\alpha 1} - t_{\alpha 0}}, \quad (2)$$

such that,

$$\theta_\alpha = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{\Delta t_{\alpha 2}}{\Delta t_{\alpha 1}} \right) = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{t_{\alpha 2} - t_{\alpha 0}}{t_{\alpha 1} - t_{\alpha 0}} \right), \quad (3)$$

where $\Delta t_{\alpha 1}$ and $\Delta t_{\alpha 2}$ are the TDOAs, $t_{\alpha 1} - t_{\alpha 0}$ and $t_{\alpha 2} - t_{\alpha 0}$, between the signals registered at points P_1 and P_2 and O , respectively. It should be noted that due to the cluster geometry, the angle estimate does not explicitly depend on wave velocity v and, therefore, on the material properties of the propagating medium. As a consequence, the angle θ_α can be computed based on measurements only, without knowing properties of the medium *a priori*. The TDOAs are time shifts between two received signals and are computed by the cross-correlation technique as

Figure 1: An arrangement of acoustic emission source, acoustic emission signals and the sensor clusters. The acoustic emission signals travel as elastic waves from the source to the sensor clusters. Here, θ_α refers to the actual arrival angle, which, owing to errors is sometimes under-predicted - $\hat{\theta}_{\alpha-}$, or over-predicted - $\hat{\theta}_{\alpha+}$.

Figure 2: Configuration of a single sensor cluster with the three sensors being placed orthogonally at points O , P_1 and P_2 .

$$\Delta t_{\alpha i} = \arg_{\tau} \max \left(\int s_0(t) s_i(t + \tau) dt \right), \quad (4)$$

where $s_0(t)$ and $s_i(t)$ are the time signals recorded O and i^{th} sensors of the sensor cluster shown in Fig. 2. Note that other techniques for computing TDOAs can be also employed [37, 38].

For acoustic source localization in isotropic homogeneous plates, for which a 2-D setup can be assumed, at least two clusters are required. The clusters are labeled with uppercase letters $\alpha = I, J, K, \dots, n$, with n being the number of clusters used for localization and hence the respective predicted arrival angles are $\theta_I, \theta_J, \theta_K$ etc. Assuming that $(x_\alpha, y_\alpha) = (x_O, y_O)^{(\alpha)}$ denote coordinates of the α^{th} cluster (i.e. the cluster position is defined through its O point) and (x_S, y_S) being the source location, the line passing through the source point and the α^{th} cluster is given as

$$y = y_\alpha + \tan(\theta_\alpha)(x - x_\alpha), \quad \alpha = I, J, K, \dots, n, \quad (5)$$

and yields a system of equations for determining the source location.

When two clusters are used for localization, i.e. $n = 2$ and $\alpha = \{I, J\}$, the set of equations (5) gives the source location at the crossing point

$$\begin{aligned} x_S &= \frac{\tan(\theta_I)x_I - \tan(\theta_J)x_J - (y_I - y_J)}{\tan(\theta_I) - \tan(\theta_J)}, \\ y_S &= y_I + \tan(\theta_I)(x_S - x_I). \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Given that $\tan(\theta_I) = \Delta t_{I2}/\Delta t_{I1}$ and $\tan(\theta_J) = \Delta t_{J2}/\Delta t_{J1}$, Eq. (6) define the source location as a function of TDOAs in the two clusters, i.e. Δt_{I1} , Δt_{I2} , Δt_{J1} and Δt_{J2} .

For acoustic emission source localization in homogeneous isotropic 2-D systems, with more than two sensor clusters, $n > 2$, the system given by Eqs. (5) is redundant, therefore requires additional treatment. In such cases, once the respective arrival angles from all the clusters are determined using the approach outlined above, it is assumed that the lines of predicted directions of arrival intersect with each other resulting in a set of points defining a polygon. The AE source location is then given by the center of mass of the polygon. For example, in AE source localization with three sensor clusters, $n = 3$, the intersections of the lines result in three points defining a triangle. The AE source location is then given by the center of mass of the triangle. For three sensor clusters labeled as I, J and K , Eq. (6) gives the three crossing points as

$$\begin{aligned} x_{S1} &= \frac{\tan(\theta_I)x_I - \tan(\theta_J)x_J - (y_I - y_J)}{\tan(\theta_I) - \tan(\theta_J)}, \\ y_{S1} &= y_I + \tan(\theta_I)(x_1 - x_I), \\ x_{S2} &= \frac{\tan(\theta_I)x_I - \tan(\theta_K)x_K - (y_I - y_K)}{\tan(\theta_I) - \tan(\theta_K)}, \\ y_{S2} &= y_I + \tan(\theta_I)(x_2 - x_I), \\ x_{S3} &= \frac{\tan(\theta_J)x_J - \tan(\theta_K)x_K - (y_J - y_K)}{\tan(\theta_J) - \tan(\theta_K)}, \\ y_{S3} &= y_J + \tan(\theta_J)(x_3 - x_J), \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where x_{Sn} and y_{Sn} , with $n \in \{1, 2, 3\}$, represent the crossing points. The three crossing points represent the three vertices of the triangle, and the AE source location is subsequently given as the center of mass

$$\begin{aligned} x_S &= \frac{x_1 + x_2 + x_3}{3}, \\ y_S &= \frac{y_1 + y_2 + y_3}{3}. \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

The procedure is analogous for $n > 3$ clusters, with properly adjusted equations for computing the center of mass of the polygon.

3. Bayesian Optimal Sensor Placement Methodology

This section introduces the Bayesian framework for optimal sensor placement for acoustic emission source localization. The objective is to find the best positions of sensor clusters for reliable estimation of source location parameter $\underline{\varphi} \in R^{n_\varphi}$ defined as $\underline{\varphi} = (x_S, y_S)$ in the 2-D plane of the plate. For this, the Bayesian inference of the source location parameters $\underline{\varphi}$ given the sensor data is first introduced. The posterior distribution of the parameter set $\underline{\varphi}$, quantifying the uncertainty in the source location parameters is then used to define an appropriate measure of information contained in a sensor configuration. Optimizing such a measure yields the optimal sensor locations.

3.1. Bayesian Inference of Source Location

Consider a set of measured data selected to be the arrival angles $D = \{\hat{\theta}_\alpha(k; \underline{\delta}_\alpha) = \tan^{-1}[\Delta\hat{t}_{\alpha 2}(k)/\Delta\hat{t}_{\alpha 1}(k)], k = 1, \dots, n_0, \alpha \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$, where α shows the cluster, $\Delta\hat{t}_{\alpha 2}(k)$ and $\Delta\hat{t}_{\alpha 1}(k)$ are the measured time differences of wave arrival defined in (3) for the arrival angle $\hat{\theta}_\alpha(k; \underline{\delta}_\alpha)$ and sensor cluster α , k denotes the sample of data, n_0 is the total number of samples in the data measured from a certain location, $\underline{\delta}_\alpha = \{x_\alpha, y_\alpha\}$ is the experimental design variables for the sensor cluster α , $\underline{\delta} = \{\underline{\delta}_1, \underline{\delta}_2, \dots, \underline{\delta}_n\}$ is the experimental design variables for all the sensor cluster locations $\alpha \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$, and n is the number of sensor clusters. The respective model predicted arrival angles $\theta_\alpha(k; \underline{\varphi}, \underline{\delta})$ is calculated by using the procedure outlined in Sec. 2. To account for the measurement and model error, the discrepancy between the measurement and the model prediction for α^{th} cluster is expressed as

$$\hat{\theta}_\alpha(k; \underline{\delta}_\alpha) = \theta_\alpha(k; \underline{\varphi}; \underline{\delta}_\alpha) + e_\alpha, \quad (9)$$

where $e_\alpha \sim N(0, \sigma_\alpha^2)$ is a zero-mean Gaussian variable with variance equal to σ_α^2 . According to the Bayesian system identification methodology, the uncertainties in the values of the parameters $\underline{\varphi}$ are quantified by the prior probability density function (PDF) $\pi(\underline{\varphi})$ and are updated using the dynamic test data D and the probability model for the prediction error e_α . Assuming independent data for each sensor cluster the updated posterior PDF of the model parameters is given by

$$p(\underline{\varphi}|D, \underline{\delta}) = \tilde{c} \frac{1}{(\sqrt{2\pi})^{nn_0} \prod_{\alpha=1}^n [\sigma_\alpha]^{n_0}} \times \exp \left[-\frac{nn_0}{2} J(\underline{\varphi}|D, \underline{\delta}) \right] \pi(\underline{\varphi}), \quad (10)$$

where

$$J(\underline{\varphi}|D, \underline{\delta}) = \frac{1}{nn_0} \sum_{\alpha=1}^n \frac{1}{\sigma_\alpha^2} \sum_{k=1}^{n_0} [\theta_\alpha(\underline{\varphi}, \underline{\delta}_\alpha) - \hat{\theta}_\alpha(k; \underline{\delta}_\alpha)]^2, \quad (11)$$

expresses the deviation between the measured and model predicted quantities. and \tilde{c} is a normalization constant guaranteeing that the posterior PDF $p(\underline{\varphi}|D, \underline{\delta})$ integrates to 1. Equation (11), quantifies the posterior uncertainty in the parameter values $\underline{\varphi}$ based on the information contained in the measured data.

3.2. Information Gain from a Sensor Configuration

The information contained in the data obtained from an experimental design $\underline{\delta}$ is quantified by relative entropy or the KL-divergence [39] between the prior and posterior PDF of the model parameter set $\underline{\varphi}$. Using utility theory [40], the optimal experimental design is accomplished by maximizing the expected information gain over all possible data generated from the prediction J error model. It can be shown that asymptotically for large number of data and small prediction errors, the utility function that measures the expected information gain from the data can be simplified as follows [41, 42, 43, 30]

$$U(\underline{\delta}) = H_\varphi - \int_\varphi H_{\varphi|D}(\underline{\delta}; \underline{\varphi}) \pi(\underline{\varphi}) d\underline{\varphi}, \quad (12)$$

where H_φ is the information entropy of the prior PDF of the source location parameters, $H_{\varphi|D}(\underline{\delta}; \underline{\varphi})$ is the information entropy of the posterior PDF of the source location parameters. For a Gaussian prior

distribution, the information entropy of the prior distribution of the source location parameters is given by

$$H_\varphi = \frac{1}{2}n_\varphi[\ln(2\pi) + 1] - \frac{1}{2}\ln\det[Q_\pi], \quad (13)$$

where the term Q_π is the inverse of the covariance matrix of the prior. For large number of data, $H_{\varphi|D}(\underline{\delta}; \underline{\varphi})$ is asymptotically approximated by the expression [23, 26]

$$H_{\varphi|D}(\underline{\delta}; \underline{\varphi}) = \frac{1}{2}n_\varphi[\ln(2\pi) + 1] - \frac{1}{2}\ln\det[Q(\underline{\delta}; \underline{\varphi}) + Q_\pi], \quad (14)$$

where $Q(\underline{\delta}; \underline{\varphi})$ is the Fisher information matrix, a semi-positive definite matrix given by

$$Q(\underline{\delta}; \underline{\varphi}) = \sum_{\alpha=1}^n \frac{1}{\sigma_e^2(\underline{\varphi}, \underline{\delta}_\alpha)} \nabla_{\underline{\varphi}}[\theta_\alpha(\underline{\varphi}; \underline{\delta}_\alpha)] \nabla_{\underline{\varphi}}^T[\theta_\alpha(\underline{\varphi}; \underline{\delta}_\alpha)], \quad (15)$$

$\nabla_{\underline{\varphi}} = [\partial/\partial x_S, \partial/\partial y_S]^T$ is the gradient operator.

Note that for one sensor cluster ($n = 1$) the Fisher information matrix defined in (15) is singular by construction. In this case significant part of the information to design an optimal sensor configuration is borrowed by the prior PDF since the inverse of the covariance matrix, Q_π , of the prior in (14) is used to avoid a zero determinant. It is obvious from the structure of (15) that at least two sensor clusters ($n \geq 2$) have to be used to avoid a singular Fisher information matrix or to design the sensor configuration for a uniform prior for which $Q_\pi = 0$.

Substituting (13) and (14) into (12), introducing the change in information entropy $\Delta H(\underline{\delta}; \underline{\varphi}) = H_\varphi - H_{\varphi|D}(\underline{\delta}; \underline{\varphi})$ between the prior and posterior distribution, the expected utility function $U(\underline{\delta})$ finally takes the form

$$U(\underline{\delta}) = \int_{\Phi} \Delta H(\underline{\delta}; \underline{\varphi}) \pi(\underline{\varphi}) d\underline{\varphi} = \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Phi} \ln \frac{\det[Q(\underline{\delta}; \underline{\varphi}) + Q_\pi]}{\det Q_\pi} \pi(\underline{\varphi}) d\underline{\varphi}, \quad (16)$$

which is an average of the change in the information entropy over the support of the prior PDF of the model parameter set $\underline{\varphi}$. The integral can be approximated with Monte Carlo or Sparse Grids methods [44, 45]

$$U(\underline{\delta}) \approx \sum_{i=1}^{n_\varphi} w_i \Delta H(\underline{\delta}; \underline{\varphi}^{(i)}) \approx \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^{n_\varphi} w_i \ln \frac{\det[Q(\underline{\delta}; \underline{\varphi}^{(i)}) + Q_\pi]}{\det Q_\pi}, \quad (17)$$

where $\underline{\varphi}^{(i)}$, $i = 1, \dots, n_\varphi$ are the sparse grid points or the samples from the prior distribution $\pi(\underline{\varphi})$ and w_i are the sparse grid or Monte Carlo weights.

3.3. Sensitivity Analysis

In order to compute the expected utility in (16), the sensitivities in (15) of the measured parameter $\theta_\alpha \equiv \theta_\alpha(\underline{\varphi}; \underline{\delta}_\alpha)$ with respect to the estimated parameters $\underline{\varphi} = (x_S, y_S)$ need to be computed. For any number of clusters, the problem is defined by Eqs. (5). Consequently, the relation $\tan(\theta_\alpha) = (y_S - y_\alpha)/(x_S - x_\alpha)$ for any θ_α can be used for calculating the sensitivities of θ_α with respect to $\underline{\varphi}$ as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \theta_\alpha}{\partial x_S} &= -\frac{y_S - y_\alpha}{L_\alpha^2}, \\ \frac{\partial \theta_\alpha}{\partial y_S} &= \frac{x_S - x_\alpha}{L_\alpha^2}, \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

where

$$L_\alpha = \sqrt{(x_S - x_\alpha)^2 + (y_S - y_\alpha)^2}, \quad (19)$$

is the distance between the source and the α^{th} sensor cluster.

3.4. Optimal Sensor Placement

The optimal sensor configuration $\underline{\delta}_{opt}$ is obtained by maximizing the utility $U(\underline{\delta})$ with respect to the design variables $\underline{\delta}$, that is

$$\underline{\delta}_{opt} = \underset{\underline{\delta}}{\operatorname{argmax}} U(\underline{\delta}). \quad (20)$$

The optimization problem is formulated as a problem involving discrete design variables $\underline{\delta}$ by introducing a regular square grid of points on the plate with all possible sensor locations assumed at the grid points. Different computationally efficient optimization methods are employing to bypass the problem of multiple local/global optima manifested in optimal experimental designs. Heuristic forward and backward sequential sensor placement (FSSP/BSSP) algorithms [46, 23], SSP (being a combination of FSSP and BSSP) [32] or genetic algorithms (GA) provide near optima solutions in a fraction of the computational effort required in exhaustive search (ES) methods [21].

3.5. Model for Prediction Error Variance σ_α^2

The prediction error variance σ_α^2 for a sensor cluster α , introduced in Equation (9) for the error term e_α , is selected to account for the model and measurement errors. The error variance for the sensor cluster α is defined as $\sigma_\alpha^2 = \theta_\alpha^2(\underline{\delta}; \varphi) \sigma^2(L_\alpha)$ to be proportional to the square of the arrival angle value predicted from the model, where $\sigma(L_\alpha)$ is the level of fractional error between the measured and predicted arrival angle value at the α^{th} cluster's position, defined with respect to the distance L_α between the source and the cluster α given in (19) as follows

$$\sigma(L_\alpha) = (\sigma_e - \sigma_0)(e^{\frac{L_0}{L_\alpha} - 1}) + \sigma_0, \quad (21)$$

σ_e is the error in the computed arrival angle for any cluster positioned at a distance L_0 from the source, and L_0 represents the distance from the source after which the assumption of plane wave front - required for the AE localization strategy proposed here - can be made. The value of L_0 is critical in determining the optimal positions of clusters, and an appropriate/reasonable value should be chosen. Although the assumption of plane wave front can be made at L_0 , it does not mean that the wave fronts are purely planar there. Consequently, some error is present in the TDOA (and subsequently the arrival angle) computations for clusters positioned at L_0 . This error is represented by σ_e . Furthermore, a very small amount of error will always exist in the arrival angle predictions at all cluster positions (irrespective of the distance of the cluster from the source) owing to the errors introduced by the usage of cross-correlation technique for TDOA computations. This small error is represented by σ_0 . It should be noted that $\sigma_e \gg \sigma_0$.

The error function given in Eq. (21) is developed in such a way that as the distance between the cluster position and the source increases, the error associated with that cluster reduces. This follows from the fact that when the distance between the source and the cluster is small, the errors introduced during arrival angle computations may result in substantial differences in the source localization predictions (Eq. (6) for 2 clusters and Eqs. (7) and (8) for 3 clusters), unlike when the clusters are far away from the source. Details regarding the values of L_0 , σ_e and σ_0 used for the predictions of optimal cluster positions in this paper are given in the following section.

4. Optimal sensor placement for AE source localization in an isotropic plate

This section reports on analytical and experimental validation of the theory proposed in Sec. 3 for optimal sensor placement for acoustic source localization. First, investigated model setup is introduced, followed by theoretical analysis and experimental validation.

4.1. Model setup

The model consisted of a $100 \times 100 \times 0.2$ cm aluminium plate with the source area in its center. The source area, rather than a source point, is employed in order to take into account the uncertainty associated with the actual AE source position in a real system. In the latter, hot-spot areas can be identified in a system based on previous structural (or other type of) analysis, not necessarily the precise point of damage initiation. The possible source location area is represented by a circle, as shown in Fig. 3. The asterisks inside the circle are the realizations of source location, i.e. actual excitation points, generated from the prior (Gaussian) distribution of the source using the Monte Carlo method, as needed for the Bayesian optimal sensor placement methodology. In the analysis that follows, three different source location areas - denoted as S_1 , S_2 , and S_3 , as shown in Fig. 3 - are explored. The possible source region S_1 (Fig. 3a) has the diameter of 1 cm, resulting in the area of 0.785 cm^2 . Such a source area is chosen with the assumption that the hot-spot lies at the center of the plate. To observe how a change in the size of the source area affects the optimal sensor cluster positions, source region S_2 (Fig. 3b) is assumed to have the diameter two times larger than that of S_1 . Consequently, the area of S_2 is four times larger than that of S_1 . Additionally, to observe how the presence of two source areas affects the optimal sensor cluster positions, S_3 comprises two areas of the source occurrence with each having the same area as S_1 (Fig. 3c). For each analyzed scenario, 200 artificial source realizations (samples) were generated for S_1 , S_3 , and S_3 (with 100 samples generated for each of the two source areas in S_3).

Both in the analytical and experimental setups, it was assumed that sensor clusters can be positioned at a discretized square grid of locations with spacing of 7.14 cm (1.5 positions per centimeter, see Fig. 3). Consequently, a total of $(225 - n)$ positions were possible, where $n = 1, 9$ and 3 for the setups presented in Figs. 3a, 3b and 3c, respectively. The distance between the grid points, representative to cluster locations, is of the order of physical dimension of a cluster of three AE sensors used in the experimental setup.

For the source localization method presented here, k (in Sec. 3) is selected to be $k = 1$. To define the measurement error required to build the prediction error term in the Bayesian optimal sensor placement methodology introduced in Sec. 3.4, we assume $\sigma_0 = 0.001$ and $\sigma_e = 20\sigma_0$ (see Eq. (21)) for all the three source areas - S_1 , S_2 and S_3 . As the source location is uncertain and represented by circular areas in our case (Fig. 3), L_0 , which defines the distance from the source at which the assumption of plane wave front can be considered, was measured from center of these source areas, and L_α defined the distance between the source and cluster location in Eq. (21). The two regions in S_3 have the same area each as the area in source S_1 . Hence, L_0 - being measured from the center of source areas - is considered the same for source areas S_1 and S_3 . However, as S_2 has a larger area than S_1 (and consequently larger area than each of the two areas in S_3), the distance L_0 for S_2 should be greater than the L_0 value used for sources S_1 and S_3 . To this effect, we assume $L_0 = 22$ cm for sources - S_1 and S_3 , and $L_0 = 28$ cm for source S_2 . The assumptions of the values of σ_0 , σ_e and L_0 chosen here were based on several preliminary studies wherein different values of σ_0 , σ_e and L_0 were tested, and the subsequent optimal cluster positions - in terms of their distance from the source areas - were observed. In these preliminary studies, a single source with realization at the center of the plate was considered. The chosen values of σ_0 , σ_e and L_0 give the optimal cluster positions at optimum distances where the plane wave front assumption can be considered, and thus the error in the computed arrival angles is minimum.

4.2. Theoretical analysis

In this section, the optimal sensor clusters positions, for the placement of 2, 3 and 4 sensors clusters, are predicted based on the theory developed in Sec. 3. Three distinct scenarios, as outlined in Sec. 4.1, corresponding to a small (S_1) and medium (S_2) hot-spots areas, and to a situation where two areas susceptible to damage coexist, are analyzed. In order to find the best and the worst cluster positions, five different methods - FSSP, BSSP, SSP, ES and GA - are used to solve the optimization problem. As the optimal sensor placement methodology is based on the information theory, the five methods' results are analyzed in terms of optimal locations of sensor clusters and computational efficiency.

Figure 3: Three different source location areas (hot-spots) explored: S_1 (a), S_2 (b), and S_3 (c)

Figures 4, 5 and 6 present the optimal and worst sensor clusters positions predicted by using the five different methods for hot-spot areas S_1 , S_2 and S_3 , respectively. In each figure the respective subplots (a), (b) and (c) illustrate the optimal (best) and worst clusters positions for the placement of 2, 3 and 4 clusters. It can be immediately observed from Figs. 4, 5 and 6 that the predictions of optimal clusters positions vary for the different search methods. The reason for this behavior is that FSSP, BSSP, SSP and GA chose one of the many near optimal solutions available, however, ES chooses the best solution owing to its 'brute-force' search approach. This causes the computational time associated with ES to increase as the number of clusters increase, as seen in Tab. 1. From Tab. 1, it can also be observed that the computational time for all the optimization methods - apart from ES - is independent from the number of optimal positions required, with FSSP and GA being the fastest. Note that Tab. 1 shows the computational times only for source S_1 ; however, the computational times required for sources S_2 and S_3 are very similar.

It can be seen from Figs. 4 and 5 that the optimal positions for the placement of 2, 3 and 4 clusters are similar for hot-spot areas S_1 and S_2 with the only difference that the optimal positions for S_2 are predicted a little farther from the center of the plate when compared with the ones obtained for S_1 . This follows from our assumption of the chosen value of L_0 being greater for S_2 than that for S_1 , as discussed in the previous section. The worst cluster positions, however, are different for S_1 and S_2 , with the worst positions for the latter occurring only around the edges of the plate.

For source areas of S_3 , the optimal and worst positions of clusters change drastically when compared to S_1 , as observed from Figs. 6 and 4. Although the two areas of S_3 have the same size as S_1 each owing to which values of L_0 assumed are the same, the predictions of the optimal clusters positions are significantly different for S_1 and S_3 . This drastic change in optimal positions is expected because the number and the location of the hot-spot areas significantly affect the optimal positions of sensor clusters. The proposed methodology is an effective technique for selecting the optimal location of sensors clusters for monitoring of multiple critical areas of a structure. The worst positions of clusters for S_3 , like in the case of S_2 (Fig. 5), occur only around the edges of the plate.

From Figs. 4-6, it can be observed that the worst clusters positions for all the source areas S_1 , S_2 and S_3 are either predicted very close to the source area or near the edges of the plate. This first scenario happens because near the source the error in the TDOA (and subsequently arrival angle) computations is significant due to the strongest deviation of the wavefront from being planar. In the case of clusters positioned at the edges of the plate, the error associated with the non-planar wavefront is small, however, the sensitivities of the arrival angles with respect to the source coordinates associated with these clusters are low because they decrease as the distance between the source and the cluster increases (see Sec. 3.3 - Eq. (18)). Note that the optimal cluster positions have the highest sensitivities and the least error. Moreover, it can be clearly seen that the worst clusters positions are co-linear with the source or very close to this setup. Consequently - owing to the cluster based localization technique used here (Sec. 2) - the

localization error is substantial due to the large difference between the predicted and the actual source locations even for a slight change in the clusters positions [16].

At the same time the best locations are relatively close to the hot-spot areas and in configurations where the clusters are at right angles to each other with respect to the source. The latter effect follows directly from the localization procedure employed here and small changes in the predicted source location when computed as the crossing of two (or more) lines with the direction coefficients computed at the clusters [16].

Figure 4: Optimal and worst sensor clusters positions for the placement of 2 (a), 3 (b), and 4 (c) clusters for source area S_1 with the legend being presented in (d).

Method	$T_{2 \text{ clusters}}$ [s]	$T_{3 \text{ clusters}}$ [s]	$T_{4 \text{ clusters}}$ [s]
FSSP	2.16	3.30	3.92
BSSP	8.02×10^3	7.95×10^3	1.22×10^3
SSP	7.68×10^3	6.99×10^3	1.23×10^3
ES	1.36×10^2	1.01×10^4	1.37×10^5
GA	22.95	22.61	34.57

Table 1: Computational times required by all the five optimization methods used here with source area S_1 . $T_{2 \text{ clusters}}$, $T_{3 \text{ clusters}}$ and $T_{4 \text{ clusters}}$ represent the computational times required to determine the optimal sensor cluster positions for the placement of 2, 3 and 4 clusters, respectively. Note that for source areas S_2 and S_3 the computational times are similar.

In the following sections, the optimal clusters positions determined are validated with theoretical and

Figure 5: Optimal and worst sensor clusters positions for the placement of 2 (a), 3 (b), and 4 (c) clusters for source area S_2 with the legend being presented in (d).

experimental approaches.

4.3. Theoretical validation - Bayesian inference

In this section, the optimal, worst and moderate sensor clusters positions for the placement of 2 and 3 sensors clusters - found in Sec. 4.2 - are analyzed and validated by employing Bayesian inference. The sensor clusters positions that result in moderate errors, i.e. better than the worst and worse than the best, were chosen by arbitrarily selecting the required number of grid points. As shown in Sec. 4.2, the different optimization methods give different (best and worst) sensor clusters positions, however, some positions are common to two or more methods (see Figs. 4-6). Hence, the best and worst sensor cluster positions chosen for the study presented here were common to at least two optimization methods. Figures 7a and 7b show the best, moderate and worst clusters positions for the placement of 2 and 3 clusters, respectively, chosen for the study presented in this section. Here, using the simulated data for an arbitrary source location in S_1 (see Fig. 3a) - $x_s = 51.5$ cm and $y_s = 47.8$ cm - the posterior distributions of the source location and the error were determined for the different types of clusters positions.

To generate the simulated data for each sensor cluster position, the actual (exact) direction of arrival (θ_α) - determined by using Eq. (5) with the chosen source location - and the measurement error value - sampled from a zero-mean Gaussian distribution with standard deviation σ_α - were taken to build the predicted directional angle of arrival ($\hat{\theta}_\alpha$). The definition of σ_α has been reported previously (see Eq.

Figure 6: Optimal and worst sensor clusters positions for the placement of 2 (a), 3 (b), and 4 (c) clusters for source areas S_3 with the legend being presented in (d).

(21)). In σ_α , the values of L_0 , σ_0 and σ_e were chosen to be 22 cm, 0.001 and 0.02, respectively, i.e., the same as for source areas S_1 and S_3 (see Sec. 4.1).

The assumed source location, (x_s, y_s) , and the error were taken as uncertain parameters. Subsequently, TMCMC sampling was used to determine their posterior distributions. For the error term, the ratio σ_0/σ_e was assumed to be constant, while σ_e was taken as uncertain. Then, Eq. (21) became $\sigma(L_\alpha) = \sigma_e((1 - \sigma_0/\sigma_e)(e^{L_0/L_\alpha - 1}) + \sigma_0/\sigma_e)$, where L_0 was assumed to be 22 cm and $\sigma_e/\sigma_0 = 20$. For the TMCMC sampling, the hard bounds of x_s , y_s and σ_e were taken as 45 – 55 cm, 45 – 55 cm and 0 – 6, respectively.

Figures 8a, 8b and 8c show the posterior distributions of the uncertain parameters, i.e. x_s , y_s and σ_e , for the best, moderate and worst clusters positions, respectively, for the placement of 2 sensor clusters; while Figs. 9a, 9b and 9c show the posterior distributions for the best, moderate and worst clusters positions for the placement of 3 sensor clusters.

It can be immediately observed from the figures that source location - x_s and y_s - distributions for the best and moderate clusters positions are normal while the distribution for the worst clusters positions is non-normal. Non-normal distributions are reflective of the cluster position giving inaccurate and unreliable results. It can also be observed from these figures that the uncertainties for the source location are the largest for the worst cluster positions and the smallest for the best cluster positions. The uncertainty for the source location computed from the moderate cluster positions are higher than the one computed for the best clusters positions, signifying that the moderate sensor cluster positions give less accurate results than the ones obtained from the best sensor cluster positions. Note that smaller uncertainty in the

values of the source coordinates represent more reliable predictions, and hence better clusters positions. Furthermore, the highest probable source location (prediction) is very near the actual source location for the best and moderate cluster positions - with the best positions predictions being the closest to the actual source location. Note that the source is assumed to be located at $x_s = 51.5$ cm and $y_s = 47.8$ cm, as shown by the red marker in Figs. 8 and 9.

Figure 7: The best, moderate and worst sensors clusters positions for the placement of 2 (a) and 3 (b) clusters chosen for the theoretical (Sec. 4.3) and experimental (Sec. 4.4) studies. (c) The source area location (S_1) used for the experimental studies (Sec. 4.4) with the 10 chosen source locations (excitation points).

4.4. Experimental validation

This section provides experimental validation of the predictions of the theoretical analysis presented in Sec. 4.2. The experimental studies were performed on a $100 \times 100 \times 0.2$ cm aluminum plate, as the one used for the theoretical analysis. The plate was equipped with a grid to facilitate placement of the AE sensors, as shown in Fig. 10. The three sensors of a cluster were placed at the nodes of the grid in a right-angle triangular configuration as in Fig. 11. The position of the cluster was defined by the position of the sensor at the right-angle vertex. The measurement system for acquiring AE signals was composed of the acquisition unit, AE sensors and preamplifiers, and was manufactured by Vallen Systeme. The excitation was provided by a pencil lead break, which is popularly used to simulate AEs in experiments.

In the study reported here, apart from the best and worst sensor clusters positions determined in the theoretical studies, the moderate sensor cluster positions - used in the theoretical validation (Sec. 4.3) - were also studied for comparison. The sensor clusters positions common to the majority of the optimization methods were chosen for experimental validation, as in the theoretical validation presented in the previous section. The source area location chosen for the experimental studies corresponded to S_1 such that 10 random points were chosen as excitation points inside source area, as shown in Fig. 7c. The

Figure 8: Posterior distributions of the uncertain parameters, i.e. the source location (x_s and y_s) and error (σ_e), for the placement of 2 clusters at the best (a), moderate (b) and worst (c) positions determined using simulated data. It can be observed that the uncertainty of the source location vary with the change in clusters positions - the best and worst positions resulting in the smallest and largest uncertainties, respectively. Note that the actual source's location is given by the red marker.

AE signals generated by these sources were recorded by the sensors' clusters at the best, moderate and worst clusters positions.

To minimize the influence of edge reflections and noise in the AE signals, appropriate threshold values and trigger conditions were set in the data measuring system. The selected conditions enabled the AE signals to be recorded by the three sensors in a cluster simultaneously as soon as the AE signals crossed the threshold of any of the three sensors. This ensured that the signals recorded at each of the three sensors belong to the AE signals generated by the pencil lead break and not edge reflections.

Using the recorded AE signals, the experimental studies were conducted using the AE source localization approach (Sec. 2) and the Bayesian inference approach. Note that the latter was performed as an extension of theoretical validation studies presented in Sec. 4.3. Details regarding data analysis of the recorded AE signals are given in the following section. Figures 7a and 7b show the best, worst and moderate sensor clusters positions for 2 and 3 clusters, respectively, chosen for the experimental studies reported here.

Figure 9: Posterior distributions of the uncertain parameters, i.e. the source location (x_s and y_s) and error (σ_e), for the placement of three clusters at the best (a), moderate (b) and worst (c) positions determined using simulated data. It can be observed that the uncertainty of the source location vary with the change in clusters positions - the best and worst positions resulting in the smallest and largest uncertainties, respectively. Note that the actual source's location is given by the red marker.

4.4.1. AE source localization approach

Using the recorded AE signals, the TDOAs were determined for each sensor cluster for all the 10 excitation points. To determine the TDOA between the sensors of a single cluster, the cross-correlation technique was used. Then, using the source localization strategy discussed previously, the respective arrival angles were determined (from the TDOAs) at the required cluster positions for all the excitation points. Then, using the cluster arrival angles in Eqs. (6) (for the placement of 2 clusters) and (7) (for the placement of 3 clusters), the source locations were predicted for best, moderate and worst sensor clusters positions. Note the difference in the strategy for AE source localization using 2 and 3 clusters.

Figures 12 and 13 show the actual and predicted source locations for the best, moderate and worst sensor clusters positions for the placement of 2 and 3 clusters, respectively. The black dashed lines depict the distance between the actual and predicted sources. It can be observed from Figs. 12 and 13 that - as expected - for certain sources, the moderate and worst sensor clusters positions' predictions are better than the best clusters positions, however, when the whole hot-spot area is considered, the predictions given by the best clusters positions is statistically better than other positions.

Tables 2 and 3 show the error between the real source locations and the source locations predicted by the best, moderate and worst sensor clusters positions with the placement of 2 and 3 clusters, respectively.

(a)

Figure 10: The $100 \times 100 \times 0.2$ cm aluminum plate used for experimental studies. The plate was equipped with a grid to facilitate placement of the AE sensors. The source area chosen for the experimental studies corresponded to S_1 , as marked on the plate.

(a)

Figure 11: Placement of (three) AE sensors at the nodes of the grid in a right-angle triangular configuration. The position of the cluster was defined by the position of the sensor at the right-angle vertex.

The error is determined as the distance between the real and predicted source locations with its average value determined by summing the errors at all the excitation points and dividing by the number of excitations used in the experimental studies, i.e. 10. The error is the smallest for the best sensor cluster positions and the highest for the worst sensor cluster positions.

From Tabs. 2 and 3 we can also see that the average error for the placement of 3 clusters is different than that of 2 clusters. This effect is related to the increase in the number of clusters, for which the AE source localization methodology changes (Sec. 2). It can be noted that increasing the number of clusters increases the amount of error in the predictions for the best case, however, the redundancy in the system (i.e. more than two clusters) improved localization accuracy for the moderate and worst case scenarios. Hence, adding more sensors clusters improves the robustness of the system and the tolerance to the sensors

Figure 12: The actual and predicted source locations - obtained using the AE source localization methodology (2) - for the best (a), moderate (b) and worst (c) clusters positions using the placement 2 clusters. The error between the real and predicted locations can be observed in Tab. 2.

Figure 13: The actual and predicted source locations - obtained using the AE source localization methodology (2) - for the best (a), moderate (b) and worst (c) clusters positions using the placement 3 clusters. The error between the real and predicted locations can be observed in Tab. 3.

placement accuracy.

As discussed previously (Sec 2), AE source localization with 3 clusters forms a triangular prediction area that represents the probable area of source location. Table 4 lists the prediction areas formed by the best, moderate and worst sensor clusters positions for all the 10 excitation locations. As expected, it can be clearly seen from Tab. 4 that the predicted area, for certain excitation points, is smallest for the moderate clusters positions; however, the average prediction area for the best clusters positions is the smallest while the average prediction area for the worst clusters positions is the largest. This suggests that the average bounds for the source location are the smallest with the best clusters positions while they are the largest with the worst clusters positions. This observation aligns with the theoretical validation presented in Sec. 4.3 where the uncertainties of the source location were the smallest for the best cluster positions and the largest for the worst clusters positions.

In the following section, the theoretical validation presented in Sec. 4.3 is repeated with experimental data.

4.4.2. Bayesian inference approach

Here, the theoretical validation study presented in Sec. 4.3 was performed with one set of experimental data from Tab. 2. In particular, the experimental data for excitation point 2 - located at $x_s = 49.2$ cm and $y_s = 50.4$ cm (see Fig. 7c) - was used to determine the posterior distributions for the uncertain parameters - i.e., the source location (x_s and y_s), and the error (σ_ϵ). Figures 14 and 15 show the posterior for the

Excitation location	Error _{Best} [cm]	Error _{Moderate} [cm]	Error _{Worst} [cm]
1	2.78	7.27	1.61
2	1.88	5.28	4.04
3	2.03	2.44	18.08
4	1.38	0.73	16.48
5	3.74	5.94	18.58
6	0.98	7.55	3.12
7	2.04	7.85	3.35
8	2.69	1.69	4.11
9	4.48	19.34	7.61
10	3.12	4.89	8.28
Average error [cm]	2.51	6.30	8.53

Table 2: Error between the actual source locations and the source locations predicted by the best, moderate and worst clusters positions for the placement of 2 clusters.

Excitation location	Error _{Best} [cm]	Error _{Moderate} [cm]	Error _{Worst} [cm]
1	2.11	2.58	9.9
2	1.13	1.05	13.97
3	2.54	4.35	10.21
4	2.12	4.41	4.93
5	3	2.67	4.48
6	7.68	1.79	3.2
7	3.53	3.69	1.34
8	7.07	9.87	23.54
9	4.55	16.03	1.28
10	4.2	2.12	2.56
Average error [cm]	3.79	4.85	7.54

Table 3: Error between the actual source locations and the source locations predicted by the best, moderate and worst clusters positions for the placement of 3 clusters.

Excitation location	Area _{Best} [cm ²]	Area _{Moderate} [cm ²]	Area _{Worst} [cm ²]
1	12.12	0.99	170.97
2	0.03	0.57	0.27
3	0.58	10.72	15.78
4	2.08	1.63	46.02
5	0.45	0.68	19.14
6	19.07	2.59	19.71
7	15.13	39.26	23.37
8	38	203.51	78.1
9	0.28	50.42	6.41
10	24.25	27.07	51.07
Average area [cm ²]	11.2	33.74	43.08

Table 4: The predicted source areas obtained by the best, moderate and worst clusters positions for the 10 excitation points using the placement of 3 clusters.

Figure 14: Posterior distributions of the uncertain parameters, i.e. the source location (x_s and y_s) and error (σ_e), for the placement of 2 clusters at the best (a), moderate (b) and worst (c) positions determined using experimental data. As in Fig. 8, it can be observed that the bounds of uncertainty of the source location vary with the change in clusters positions - the best and worst positions resulting in the smallest and largest bounds, respectively. Note that the actual source's location is given by the red marker.

Figure 15: Posterior distributions of the uncertain parameters, i.e. the source location (x_s and y_s) and error (σ_e), for the placement of 3 clusters at the best (a), moderate (b) and worst (c) positions determined using experimental data. As in Fig. 9, it can be observed that the bounds of uncertainty of the source location vary with the change in clusters positions - the best and worst positions resulting in the smallest and largest bounds, respectively. Note that the actual source's location is given by the red marker. The absence of red marker in Fig. 15c indicates that the actual source is far away from the Bayesian prediction.

placement of 2 and 3 clusters, respectively. Note that for the study presented here, the hard bounds of x_s , y_s and σ_e were 40 – 60 cm, 40 – 60 cm and 0 – 6, respectively, for the TMCMC sampling.

From Figs. 14 and 15, it can be observed, like in Figs. 8 and 9, that the uncertainties of source location are the smallest for the best clusters positions while the uncertainties are the largest for the worst clusters positions, with the uncertainties in the moderate clusters positions being closer to those of the best positions. Moreover, we can further see from Figs. 14 and 15 that the estimated most probable source location is relatively very near to the actual source location (shown by the red marker in Figs. 14 and 15) for the best and moderate clusters positions when compared with those of the worst positions - with the predictions from the best cluster positions being the closest to the actual source locations. Note that the absence of red marker in Fig. 15c indicates that the actual source is far away from the Bayesian prediction.

The posterior distributions presented in Figs. 14 and 15 corroborate our results obtained with simulated data in Figs. 8 and 9 and further validate our findings regarding the best and worst sensor clusters positions presented in Sec. 4.2.

5. Conclusions

In this paper, the optimal and worst sensor clusters positions were obtained for AE source localization in an isotropic plate by employing Bayesian optimal sensor placement methodology. Three different hot-spot (source location) areas were analyzed such that the best and worst clusters positions were determined for the placement of 2, 3 and 4 sensor clusters. The Bayesian optimal sensor methodology requires solving an optimization problem, and in this paper, five different methods were employed and compared in terms of the optimal (and worst) locations of sensor clusters and computational efficiencies. It was observed that the computational time and even the locations of the best (and worst) clusters positions depend on the optimization method used. The differences in the optimal (worst) cluster positions are due to the fact that these methods are approximate. One expects that these optimal cluster positions provided by the different optimization methods are near optima cluster positions corresponding to utility values close to the maximum utility. Moreover, as expected, it was shown that with the change in source area locations, the positions of the best and worst clusters changes.

To validate the optimal and worst clusters positions provided by the Bayesian optimal sensor placement methodology, we first performed theoretical validation followed by experimental validation. The former involved using Bayesian inference with simulated data while the latter involved using experimental data with AE source localization methodology - which is commonly used for AE source localization studies - and Bayesian inference. For the validation studies (both theoretical and experimental), moderate clusters positions, which give results better than the worst and worse than the best clusters positions, were also considered to compare with the best and worst clusters positions.

The AE source localization methodology involved using TDOAs for each sensor cluster to predict the source locations, while the Bayesian inference involved using TMCMC sampling to determine the posterior distributions of the source location. From AE source localization methodology, it was observed that the error is the smallest for the best sensor cluster positions and the highest for the worst sensor cluster positions - with the moderate cluster positions giving error higher than the best positions and smaller than the worst positions. From the Bayesian inference, it was observed that the best sensor cluster positions for predicting the source location outperform the predictions provided by the moderate and worst sensor cluster positions. As expected, the performance of the worst sensor cluster positions was the worst in predicting the source location. It was also observed that uncertainties of the source location were the smallest for the best and largest for the worst sensor clusters positions, while the moderate clusters positions predicted uncertainties between those of the best and worse clusters positions. The observations from Bayesian inference - being consistent with both the simulated and experimental data - and AE source localization methodology validated our results about the best and worst clusters positions obtained using the Bayesian optimal sensor placement methodology.

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θ [deg]	Error [deg]								
	$R = 3B$	$R = 3.5B$	$R = 4B$	$R = 4.5B$	$R = 5B$	$R = 5.5B$	$R = 6B$	$R = 6.5B$	$R = 7B$
0	9.46	7.13	7.13	7.13	4.76	4.57	4.57	4.57	4.57
2	9.77	7.46	7.46	7.46	4.84	4.84	4.84	4.84	4.84
4	10.04	7.77	7.77	7.77	5.46	5.46	5.46	5.46	5.46
6	32.37	8.04	8.04	5.77	5.77	5.77	5.77	5.77	3.46
8	30.37	31.81	8.26	6.04	6.04	6.04	6.04	3.77	3.77
10	29.81	31.19	8.43	6.26	6.26	6.26	6.26	4.04	4.04
12	41.13	27.81	6.43	6.43	6.43	6.43	4.26	4.26	4.26
14	40.29	25.81	6.56	6.56	4.43	4.43	4.43	4.43	4.43
16	39.12	25.19	26.4	4.56	4.56	4.56	4.56	5.37	4.56
18	37.92	24.4	24.4	24.4	24.4	3.37	3.37	3.37	3.37
20	25	23.73	23.73	22.4	22.4	1.37	1.37	22.4	1.37
22	45.38	23	23	21.73	21.73	21.73	23	21.67	0.25
24	4.61	41.38	2.57	22.27	7.61	7.61	7.61	7.61	7.61
26	29.3	26.43	2.61	10.03	11.15	7.57	7.57	7.03	7.03
28	43.57	26.46	5.89	5.25	11.99	6.84	4.57	6.84	6.84
30	47.91	113.88	11.99	4.98	4.98	12.95	12.95	5.85	11.88
32	13	2.62	2.62	12.35	13	13	13	13	13
34	12.91	12.97	2.19	14.01	13.05	13.05	13.05	13.05	14.12
36	12.29	12.37	1.78	13.09	13.09	14.19	13.09	1.78	14.19
38	1.52	2.24	14	2.1	15.13	14.25	1.13	1.13	2.69
40	1.08	0.97	1.82	13.97	13.13	14.29	14.29	0.44	1.95
42	13.56	12.78	13.92	13.12	1.36	14.31	13.12	14.31	14.31
44	12.31	12.69	13.09	13.85	13.09	13.09	0.17	0.17	0.17
46	12.57	12.57	13.74	13.04	13.04	0.17	0.17	0.64	0.17
48	11.26	12.42	11.74	12.95	11.74	0.51	11.74	0.51	12.95
50	1.34	11.61	11.61	11.61	11.61	11.61	1.63	12.82	12.82
52	1.84	11.43	0.77	11.43	0.77	10.82	12.06	12.06	12.06
54	1.3	1.3	1.3	2.82	10.65	11.9	10.65	11.9	10.65
56	1.8	1.8	3.57	14.12	2.39	11.69	2.39	2.63	2.39
58	3.94	3.94	2.99	2.99	14.04	2.99	14.04	13	2.02
60	4.33	4.33	13.96	13.96	13.96	13.96	3.37	12.88	3.02
62	5.37	5.37	4.38	4.38	4.38	3.37	3.37	3.37	3.37
64	5.76	5.76	4.76	4.76	4.76	3.74	3.74	3.74	3.74
66	6.17	6.17	5.74	4.14	4.14	4.71	4.71	3.1	3.1
68	7.17	5.6	6.14	6.14	5.1	4.03	4.03	4.03	2.94
70	7.6	6.57	6.57	5.51	5.51	4.44	4.44	3.36	3.36
72	8.57	7.51	7.51	6.44	5.36	5.36	4.25	4.25	4.25
74	9.02	7.96	6.89	5.8	5.8	4.7	4.7	10.92	3.98
76	8.89	8.89	6.7	6.7	8.92	4.43	4.43	4.43	3.28
78	10.89	8.7	7.57	6.43	10.73	4.11	4.11	4.11	4.11
80	5.03	8.06	7.28	5.78	4.93	3.74	3.74	3.74	3.74
82	4.27	7.78	7.78	6.62	5.45	3.07	4.26	4.26	3.31
84	10.93	7.45	6.26	6.26	5.07	5.07	3.87	3.87	3.87
86	173.51	7.07	7.07	5.87	5.87	5.87	4.65	3.43	6.01
88	7.87	6.65	6.65	6.65	5.43	5.43	4.2	4.2	4.2
90	8.65	7.43	7.43	6.2	6.2	6.2	4.97	4.97	6.71
Average Error [deg]	18.71	14.66	8.45	9.18	8.71	7.35	6.39	6.38	5.53

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